

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

IMPACT OF CLINICAL PHARMACIST MEDIATED CARE IN DIABETES MELLITUS - A NEW COMMUNITY BASED MODEL OF CARE

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 18/05/2017

Available online
30/06/2017

Keywords

Diabetes Mellitus,
Glycemic Control,
Quality Of Life,
Medication Adherence,
HBA1C.

ABSTRACT

AIMS: The main Aim of the study is to evaluate the impact of clinical pharmacist care in improving glycemic control, HRQOL, medication adherence in type 2 Diabetes mellitus patients. **METHODS:** The study is conducted in government general hospital, Guntur, a territory care hospital and it is a prospective comparative observational study including 100 subjects with type 2 diabetes mellitus out of these 50 were randomly assigned in to test group and 50 in to the control group. **RESULTS:** By observing the data, glycaemic control in the test population is clearly improved with a mean difference of -57.18 and p value of < 0.0001 i.e., extremely significant when compared to the control population with a mean difference of -7.68 and p value of 0.8694 i.e., nil significant. There is better glycaemic control with respect to the HbA1c levels in the test population with a mean difference of 1.8 and p value of < 0.0001 i.e., extremely significant than the control population with a mean difference of 7.68 and p value of 0.216 i.e., nil significant. There is a predominant improvement in quality of life of test population with a mean difference in QOL score 32.81±0.9045 and p value <0.0001 i.e., statistically extremely significant when compared to the control percentage score with a mean difference of 7.647±1.545 and p value < 0.01 i.e., statistically significant. There is major increase in medication adherence in the test group with a mean difference of 4.3±0.603 and p value < 0.0001 i.e., extremely significant when compared to the control with a mean difference of 1.2±0.15 and p value < 0.549 which is statistically nil significant. **CONCLUSION:** The study provide information regarding impact of glycemic control on QOL and medication adherence in type 2 DM patients. We conclude that clinical pharmacist together with physician play a major role in improving the glycaemic control and medication adherence in type 2 DM patients which directly shows impact on health related quality of life.

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Please cite this article in press as **G. Mounika** et al. Impact of Clinical Pharmacist Mediated Care in Diabetes Mellitus - A New Community Based Model of Care. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(06).

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a common, costly condition associated with significant morbidity and mortality [1, 2]. Recent studies have found dramatic increases in diabetes during the last decade [3]. Diabetes self-management education (DSME), the process of teaching individuals to manage their diabetes [4], has been considered as an important part of the clinical management of individuals with diabetes since the 1930s and the work of the Joslin Diabetes Centre [5]. The American Diabetes Association recommends assessment of self-management skills and knowledge of diabetes at least annually, and the provision or encouragement of continuing diabetes education [6]. One of the diabetes-related objectives of Healthy People 2010[7] is to increase to 60%, from the 1998 baseline level of 40%, the proportion of individuals with diabetes who receive formal diabetes education. The goals of self-management education are to optimize metabolic control, prevent acute and chronic complications, and optimize quality of life, while keeping costs acceptable [8]. There are significant knowledge and skill deficits in 50–80% of patients with diabetes [9], and ideal glycaemic control (HbA1c<7.0) is achieved in less than half of individuals with type 2 diabetes [10]. A large body of literature has developed on diabetes education and its efficacy, including several important quantitative reviews showing positive effects of diabetes education. However, educational techniques have evolved over the last decade since these reviews [11-13], and they have shifted from didactic presentations to interventions involving patient “empowerment” [14, 15] with participation and collaboration.

The International Diabetes Federation predicts that the number of people living with diabetes will rise from 366 million in 2011 to 552 million by 2030.^[16] In the United States, the prevalence of diagnosed diabetes has more than doubled in the last 3 decades, largely because of the increase in obesity.

PATIENT EDUCATION AND MEDICATION COUNSELING:-

- Patient who receive diabetes education, medication counselling and instruction on diet, exercise, and regular monitoring of blood glucose monitoring by a pharmacist in an integrated primary care setting can be benefited by
 - Improved glycemic control.
 - Greater adherence to prescribed therapy.
 - Clinical pharmacist care and the expanded role of pharmacist have been associated with many positive diabetes-related outcomes, improved glycemic control, improved patient and provider satisfaction and improved cost management.

Diabetes as a disease may be experienced in different ways around the world. In a large review, “Quality of life and diabetes”, by Rubin and Peyrot, it was stated that significant associations have been demonstrated between socioeconomic status and HRQOL in the general population, while no significant association has been found between race and ethnicity and HRQOL among people with diabetes^[17]. Furthermore, differences in outcomes have been found when comparing different healthcare systems in the USA^[18]. However, less is known as regards differences in HRQOL in different regions of the world.

CLINICAL PHARMACIST CARE IN MANAGEMENT OF DIABETES MELLITUS:

- Pharmaceutical care is the direct, responsible provision of medication- related care for the purpose of achieving definite outcomes that improve a patient’s quality of life.
- Pharmacist care is a process through which a pharmacist works with other health care professionals and the patient to optimize pharmacotherapy.
- Clinical pharmacist care and the expanded role of pharmacist have been associated with many positive diabetes-related outcomes, improved glycemic control, improved patient and provider satisfaction and improved cost management.
- Pharmacist based diabetes programs that are integrated in to primary care practice reduced A1C levels by an average of 1.9 percent over 6 months. [18] Pharmacy care has been associated with decreased direct medical costs of \$1,200 per year and an estimated annual increase in productivity of \$18,000 due to reduction in blood sugars.

DIABETES AND QUALITY OF LIFE:

The research field in quality of life (QOL) has increased enormously since 1990. As QOL represents the effect of an illness on a patient, as perceived by the patient, and yields complementary information to medical or epidemiological data, it is often used as an outcomes measurement. QOL has also been characterized as “the ultimate goal of all health interventions” [19]. QOL is a concept that covers a broad range of human experience. In the medical domain it denominates aspects of the health from the patient’s or subject’s point of view, and could better be expressed as “subjective health” or “functional status and wellbeing”. In this article the term “health-related quality of life” (HRQOL) will be used. Diabetes is one of the most important chronic diseases in the population, when regarding the Impact on health. Most diabetic patients, i.e. especially those with type 2 diabetes, are cared for in primary health care. Diabetes is connected with vascular complications, and in international and national guidelines the overall goal for the treatment of all diabetes is to prevent acute and chronic complications, while preserving a good quality of life for the patient. Thus, knowledge concerning HRQOL in diabetic patients, as well as the determinants of this, is crucial. Diabetes as a disease may be experienced in different ways around the world. In a large review, “Quality of life and diabetes”, by Rubin and Peyrot, it was stated that significant associations have been demonstrated between socioeconomic status and HRQOL in the general population, while no significant association has been found between race and ethnicity and HRQOL among people with diabetes[19]. Furthermore, differences in outcomes have been found when comparing different healthcare systems in the USA [20]. However, less is known as regards differences in HRQOL in different regions of the world.

OBJECTIVES:-

1. To minimize the complications of diabetes with proper education and pharmaceutical care.
2. To evaluate the quality of life in diabetic patients during improved glycaemic control by using a previously validated quality of life instrument.
3. To provide the clinical pharmacist care to study group which is to be compared with control group.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:-**STUDY DESIGN:-**

A prospective observational study

STUDY PERIOD:-

6months from January2016- June2016.

STUDY PLACE:-

Government General Hospital, Guntur, a 1200 bedded tertiary care hospital.

STUDY SAMPLE:-

100 Patients diagnosed with DM.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:-

- All the patients of either gender diagnosed with diabetes mellitus as the chief reason For hospital visit.
- Patients included are of age group of above 21 years.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:-

- Children, pregnant women are excluded.
- Mentally incompetent and critically ill patients are excluded from the study.
- Patients with other co morbidities except hypertension are excluded from the study.

PLAN OF WORK:**PHASE I: PREPARATION OF MATERIALS:-**

- Patient consent form
- Data collection form
- Diabetic diet chart
- QOLID instrument
- Medication adherence scale
- Diabetic alert cards

Power point presentations and visuals

PHASE II:

Ethical committee approval

PHASE III:

Selection of subjects-100 Patients were selected based on inclusion and exclusion criteria and an informed consent was taken and the data is tabulated and analysed.

PHASE IV:**FOR TEST GROUP:**

On 1st Visit or follow up

1. Base line blood sugar, HbA1c levels were monitored.
2. 50 Test Patients were counselled regarding Diabetes, its complications through leaflets. Medication Adherence.
3. Diabetic Diet by providing diet chart, Diet classes by dietician, visuals.
4. Physical Exercise including practice of yoga.
5. Counselling to the care taker.
6. QOLID questionnaire was provided and feedback was collected.
7. Morisky medication adherence scale was provided and feedback was collected.

FOR CONTROL GROUP:

1. Base line blood sugar, HbA1c levels were monitored.
2. QOLID questionnaire was provided and feedback was collected.
3. Morisky medication adherence scale was provided and feedback was collected.

Observations and results:

Graph.1: Age wise total population

Graph.2: Gender Description of Total Population.

Graph.3: Educational status in test group.

Graph.4: Educational status in control group.

Graph.5: Food habits in test group

Graph.6: Food habits in control group.

Graph.7: Social habits in test group

Graph.8: Social habits in control group.

Graph.9: Therapy used in test group

Graph.10: Therapy used in control group.

FBS Analysis

Table.1: Test FBS levels.

Parameters	1st follow up	2nd follow up	3rd follow up	4th follow up
MEAN	172.92	155.26	133.04	115.74
SD	54.754	40.66	36.24	22.48
SEM	7.74	5.75	5.12	3.17
P Value	< 0.0001****			

Table.2: Control FBS levels.

Parameters	1st follow up	2nd follow up	3rd follow up	4th follow up
MEAN	164.84	171.42	170.9	172.52
SD	52.99	51.26	47.04	48.456
SEM	7.49	7.250	6.653	6.853
P Value	0.8694 NS			

Fig.11: Test FBS levels.

Fig.12: Control FBS levels.

PPBS Analysis:

Table.3: Test PPBS levels.

Parameters	1st follow up	2nd follow up	3rd follow up	4th follow up
MEAN	271.8	235.5	200.16	172.36
SD	81.89	56.60	47.47	34.38
SEM	11.58	8	6.71	4.86
P Value	< 0.0001****			

Table.4: Control PPBS levels.

Parameters	1st follow up	2nd follow up	3rd follow up	4th follow up
MEAN	265.72	282.2	285.8	275.5
SD	91.0	85.42	79.0	71.35
SEM	12.875	12.081	11.179	10.090
P Value	< 0.6287*			

Fig.13: Test PPBS levels.

Fig.14: Control PPBS levels.

HbA1C:

Table.5: Test HbA1c levels.

Parameters	Before study	After study
MEAN	9.688	7.842
SD	1.847	1.284
SEM	0.2612	0.1816
P Value	< 0.0001****	

Table.6: Control HbA1c levels.

Parameters	Before study	After study
MEAN	9.57	10.06
SD	2.0	1.92
SEM	0.284	0.272
P Value	< 0.216NS	

Fig.15: Test HbA1c levels.

Fig.16: Control HbA1c levels.

QUALITY OF LIFE

Table.7: Quality of life for test group.

Parameters	Before	After
MEAN	43.146	75.95
SD	4.08	4.922
SEM	0.57	0.69
P Value	< 0.0001****	

Table.8: Quality of life for control patients.

Parameters	Before	After
MEAN	46.8	54.52
SD	5.464	9.458
SEM	0.7728	1.338
P Value	< 0.01**	

Fig.17: Quality of life for test group

Fig.18: Quality of life for control patients.

MEDICATION ADHERENCE

Fig.19: MA in test group.

MEDICATION ADHERENCE: CONTROL

Fig.20: MA in control group.

DISCUSSION

A total of 100 patients were recruited in to the study based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Out of these 50 Subjects were randomly assigned in test group and the rest in control group.

The mean age of study population was 53.63 ± 9.5 years. Considering the gender, 66% of patients were female and 34% were male. While considering literacy, there were 32% illiterates, 19% literate and 49% low literates. The duration of diabetes was 5.5 ± 5.12 years (min: 1, max: 24). 99% of subjects were controlling the disease by oral hypoglycaemic agents and diet, and 1% by insulin, oral diabetics and diet. This findings were similar to the study conducted by AlirezaShahab Jahanlou1 et al, in which 67.5% of patients were female and 32.5% were male. The mean age was 49.15 ± 9.5 years (min: 27 max: 72). The rate of literacy, there were (42.1%) illiterates, 39% low literates and 19% literate. 4.8% used to control the disease only by diet, 81.5% by oral hypoglycaemic and diet, and 13.7% by insulin and diet. Most of the study population were prescribed with metformin in combination with glimepiride (38%) followed by metformin alone (35%). 6% of our study population had complication of diabetic neuropathy. The food habits were 90% of the population were non vegetarians and 10% are vegetarians intervening more disease prevalence in non-vegetarians. This findings were supported by a study conducted in Indian population by Sutapa Agrawal et al ' concluded that Consumption of a vegetarian diet was associated with a lower likelihood of diabetes than a non-vegetarian diet in the adjusted analyses.

Although many studies have focused on the long term benefits of glycaemic control in diabetes complications, this study demonstrated the short term symptomatic relief, improvement in QOL associated with improved glycaemic control in patients with type 2 DM. We also observed that a strong relationship between improved glycaemic control and the beneficial changes in QOL in our test population compared to that of control population with poor or no improved glycaemic control, suggesting that the rate of QOL decoration due to worsening glycaemic control. These findings were similar to an American study conducted by Marica A Testa and Simonson' In addition, fasting blood glucose levels and post prandial blood sugar levels were almost identical from baseline to the endpoint for the control group, the corresponding QOL score haven't shown much difference substantially.

In this study we found that there is a greater improvement in health related QOL in patients with HbA1c levels of < 7.0%. These findings are similar to the study conducted by Wikblad K, Leksell J, Wibell L. et al which implied lowest QOL in patients with the highest HbA1c levels (>8.1%), highest in those with HbA1c levels 7.1-8% and intermediate in those with the lowest HbA1c levels (<7.0%).^[20] we found that there was no difference in HRQOL based on gender in type DM patients. This result was consistent with the study conducted by Grace Lindey et al. In our study population we found that improvement in QOL is more in females than that of the males. This result is similar to the STUDY conducted by Grace Lindsay et al., which suggested that the QOL in male subjects with type 2 DM is low.

We used QOLID questionnaire for the assessment of HRQOL developed and validated by jitendernagpal et al. QOLID is a reliable, valid and sensitive tool for the assessment of diabetes specific quality of life in Indian subjects. The HRQOL improvements were both consistent and substantial across all major 8 domains of the questionnaire in test population when compared to the control group.

By analysing the data, it is clear that Medication adherence showing a major impact on improved glycaemic control. In our study we observed non adherence to the medications in major subjects in both the test and control population at baseline. At the end point there is predominant improvement in the medication adherence in test population who received counselling and education regarding the medication use and had a better glycaemic control when compared to that of the control population. Literacy also played an important role in improving adherence in our study subjects. Literates are more self-efficient towards medication adherence than the low literates and illiterates. These findings are similar to the study conducted by A. ShahabJahanlou and N. AlishanKarami on “The Effect of Literacy Level on Health Related-Quality of Life, Self-Efficacy and Self-Management Behaviours in Diabetic Patients”.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results we conclude that clinical pharmacist together with physician play a major role in improving the glycaemic control and medication adherence in type 2 DM patients which directly shows impact on health related quality of life. Our study also suggest that a successful program requires more than educational sessions with dieticians and a manual of instruction on glycaemic control. We conducted a comprehensive program with multidisciplinary team members engaged with patients on a regular basis which lead to a significant T2DM patients to achieve a meaningful glycaemic control.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS:

This study is focused mainly on Medication adherence, diet, physical exercise has the major measures for improving glycaemic control, and it is further suggested to include dose adjustments based on the glycaemic levels to be include in future studies.

ABBREVIATIONS

HRQOL	: Health related quality of life,
QOLID	: Quality of life in Indian diabetics,
T2DM	: Type 2 diabetes mellitus,
HBA1C	: Glycosylated haemoglobin,
MA	: Medication adherence,
FBS	: Fasting blood sugar,
PPBS	: post prandial blood sugar,
RBS	: Random blood sugar.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We wish to express heartfelt thanks to Dr. D. S. Raju Naidu MD., RT, Superintendent, Government General Hospital, Guntur, Dr B. Sailaja MD, Mrs P. Sharmila Nirojini and to our parents for their constant support and encouragement.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST:

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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